

Automated Solutions for Sustainable and Circular Construction and Demolition Waste Management

4th E-NEWSLETTER | January 2024

Greetings and a Happy New Year to our esteemed partners and followers!

We are very happy to share with you, in this first issue for 2024, the news and information about our research progress. The first RECONMATIC deliverable is submitted, bringing some insights on the implementation of circularity in the construction sector across Europe, while two new scientific publications during the past months explain how machine learning and blockchain can contribute to sustainable construction.

In this issue, you will also read about the “mystery” behind the 1st Open Day of the RECONMATIC Project at the Czech Researchers’ Night and the visit of our Chinese partners to the partners’ premises in Prague. You will have the chance to meet the people behind the project by following #RECONMATICTeam on social media and learn more about two more projects in synergy with RECONMATIC!

Our Blog section hosts an article in Czech, about the RECONMATIC project and the technologies developed by the partners, which was included in the Tecnicall magazine.

Last but not least, you will learn about our dissemination activities and have updates on the partners’ participation in important industry events across Europe, as well as, be informed on what is coming up in the following months.

[Subscribe](#) to our newsletter to receive all the updates in your inbox and feel free to share the news.

Enjoy the read!

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NEWS

RECONMATIC unveils insights on Circular Economy Implementation & calls for stakeholders contribution

The first deliverable of the RECONMATIC project is submitted and provides insights that can be considered as a first step for the assessment of circularity across Europe and provide a baseline for the Guidance and Assessment tool that has already started being developed by RECONMATIC. Several challenges were identified but so are some recommendations for the future! The next steps are already in progress and you can be part of them!

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC in the Czech Researchers' Night in Prague

The first Open Day of the project was proudly hosted by the Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU) as part of the Czech European Researchers' Night. The RECONMATIC project gave a twist of Construction and Demolition waste recycling to the topic for this year, which was "Mystery", by organising an engaging, non-technical, introduction to the RECONMATIC project including video and new construction materials presentations.

[Learn more](#)

Project partners from China visit the RECONMATIC facilities in the Czech Republic

The representatives of the esteemed RECONMATIC partners from China, embarked on an insightful journey in the Czech Republic, after joining the 2nd annual project meeting in Manchester.

They had the opportunity to visit the partners' premises for research and recycling of Construction and demolition waste and were updated about the current status and the national initiatives in the sector.

[Learn more](#)

Meet the RECONMATIC Team

Jan Valentin
Deputy Head and Senior Researcher
Czech Technical University in Prague (CZ)

The #ReconmaticTeam Campaign presenting the project coordinator

As our #ReconmaticTeam social media campaign is over, we would like to give you the chance to meet the people who work “behind the scenes” during all the previous months and will keep collaborating until the end of the project. You can visit our social media using the hashtag #ReconmaticTeam on [LinkedIn](#) and [X \(Twitter\)](#) and meet all the members of our consortium.

[Learn more](#)

SYNERGIES

In preparation of our clustering event in the end of February, RECONMATIC is excited to present two more projects not only aligned with our goals but also with already established synergies with our project.

CircularB Cost Action: Implementation of Circular Economy in the Built Environment

RECONMATIC has been working jointly with CircularB Cost Action for several months, with three of our partners - ICATALIST and the universities in Prague, Czechia (CTU) and in Thessaloniki, Greece (AUth) - participating in their team. We have already launched research on construction stakeholders' views and a search for key performance indicators on circularity, and we continue working with CircularB on the development of an international circularity framework for the inclusive operation and assessment of new and existing buildings.

Stay tuned for more on our joint actions.

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC in the CircularB Workshop on Circularity in the Built Environment

Our partner ICATALIST S.L actively participated in the last workshop organised by the CircularB team, entitled "Creating a Roadmap towards Circularity in the Built Environment - State-of-the-Art."

[Learn more](#)

ICEBERG Project: Innovative Circular Economy Based solutions for the building industry

The Iceberg Project, coordinated by our partner TECNALIA, shares our vision for circularity in construction and is in close collaboration with the RECONMATIC team. Let's learn more about their approach.

[Learn more](#)

PUBLICATIONS

Machine-learning-assisted classification of construction and demolition waste fragments using computer vision

Reconmatic
#TECHNOLOGY

Machine-learning-assisted classification of CDW fragments using computer vision

Funded by the European Union

Concrete

This new study, published by the Faculty of Civil Engineering of the Czech Technical University in Prague, provides findings that have significant implications for the future of

CDW management and includes materials that promote transparency and reproducibility.

[Learn more](#)

Scientific paper at BlockSecSDN workshop at ICC 2023

Read more on Hyperledger Fabric, a popular enterprise-grade blockchain framework that falls into the category of the permissioned blockchains, making it particularly effective at ensuring transparency for secure communication among peers, such as the SDN controllers of an IoT network.

[Learn more](#)

BLOG

RECONMATIC in the Czech TecniCall magazine

Read an informative article on the RECONMATIC project and the technologies developed, by our project coordinator, the Czech Technical University in Prague in the latest issue of the TecniCall magazine (in Czech language).

[Learn more](#)

EVENTS

8th International Academic Conference on Places and Technologies

Our partners from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki participated in the 8th International Academic Conference on Places and Technologies in Belgrade, Serbia and talked about the implementation of circularity principles in the built environment.

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC at the Digitalisation, Circular Economy and Infrastructure Workshop at the University of Manchester

Partners involved: University of Manchester

Our partners at the University of Manchester successfully organised and hosted the workshop on the “Digitalisation, Circular Economy and Infrastructure” on the 23rd of November 2023. Prof. Yong Wang and Dr Muhammad Omer emphasised the necessity of circularity in construction and presented aspects of the RECONMATIC project.

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC in Horizon Europe Info Day on Cluster 4, "Industry and Space", Spain

Partners involved: Tecnalia, RECSO

Javier Llorente from RECSO and Inés Díez Ortiz from Tecnalia, participated at the event where the focus was on the open calls for 2024 of Cluster 4 for the areas of "INDUSTRY AND SPACE". Our two partners presented RECONMATIC's approach on digitalisation and integrated decision-making that considers all aspects of CDW generation.

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC presented in the Waste Forum - 17th Czech-Slovak Symposium

Partners involved: Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU), STRABAG

The RECONMATIC partners Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU) and STRABAG co-organised the very interesting “Conference on Waste from and for the construction Industry” that took place in the Czech Republic, and proudly presented the project to key stakeholders including important authorities’ representatives.

[Learn more](#)

V. International Conference Progress of Recycling in the Built Environment, Germany

Partners involved: Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU)

Amidst the historic backdrop of Weimar, Václav Nežerka (CTU) presented a breakthrough study at the “V. International Conference Progress of Recycling in the Built Environment”. The event, organised by the Weimar Institute of Applied Construction Research in Germany, carved out new pathways for the construction sector's future.

[Learn more](#)

Upcoming Activities

Meanwhile, all the partners are planning their participation in the following sector events all around Europe and the globe. They will be glad to meet you in person and discuss more about the RECONMATIC innovations and vision.

- The Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU-project coordinator) will represent RECONMATIC in the 7th CIGOS: "Advances in Planning, Architecture and Construction for Sustainable Development" in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, on April 4-5, 2024.
- The ANAKEM will join the 1st OPEN-AIR CITIES International Conference, "Local and Regional #SustainableDevelopment and Urban Reconstruction" in Athens, Greece on 16-18 February 2024.

Last but not least, the RECONMATIC partners are already masterminding the **2nd Open Day in Manchester on May 7th, 2024**.

Save the date and stay tuned via the project's social media channels on [LinkedIn](#) (@RECONMATIC) and [X \(Twitter\)](#) (@reconmatic) to never miss any updates on our activities!

[Subscribe](#) to our website to receive directly in your inbox all the updates about the deliverables and the papers soon to be published, as well as the project activities and progress.

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OUR PARTNERS

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UK Research and Innovation

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